

Title	International access modalities recommendations for 2030 in ATMO-ACCESS RIs, based on test cases
Work package n°	3
Milestone/Deliverable n°	D3.4
Lead beneficiary	UHEL
Author(s)	Tuukka Petäjä, Sabine Philippin, Ulla Wandinger, Ilona Ylivinkka, Silja Häme, Matilde Oliveri, Ariane Dubost, Jakub Ondracek, Jochen Wagner, Rosa Petracca Altieri and Carmela Cornacchia
Deliverable Type	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Estimated delivery date	M48
Actual delivery date	15 th May 2025
Version	1
Reviewed by	Iwona Stachlewska (UW) Sabine Philippin (CNRS)
Accepted by	Paolo Laj (WMO)
Comments	

Table of content

1.	<i>Introduction</i>	3
2.	<i>Evaluation and analysis of challenges</i>	4
2.1	Fragmented European funding landscape	4
2.2	Legal and administrative barriers.....	5
2.3	Limitations in institutional mandates and operational models.....	5
2.4	Geopolitical constraints.....	7
2.5	Lack of Global Reciprocity and Balanced Partnerships	7
3.	<i>Recommendations for International Access Modalities</i>	9
3.1	Towards Sustainable and Inclusive Funding Mechanisms	9
3.2	Harmonizing Access Policies and Procedures.....	10
3.3	Enhancing Monitoring and Impact Assessment.....	10
3.4	Strengthening Global Collaboration and Reciprocity	11
3.5	Clarifying the Relationship Between Access and Open Data	11
3.6	Strategic Planning and Stakeholder Engagement.....	12
4.	<i>Conclusions and Outlook</i>	12
5.	<i>References</i>	13

1. Introduction

Atmospheric Research Infrastructures (RI) are international by nature. They are involved in supporting research of pressing global challenges such as climate change and air quality deterioration. The atmospheric RIs provide key observational capacities to monitor and study these phenomena. Open data from the RIs, open science and active collaborations across different boundaries, such as scientific domains and national borders, are required to address these grand challenges.

Atmospheric research facilities of the RIs are generally operated at a national level. The scientific collaboration is supported by TransNational Access (TNA) to these national facilities (NFs). TNA is, by definition, access to RI services across the national boundaries. In the widest sense, it includes global access to RIs. However, in practice, the current regulations governing access under EC-funded, project-based schemes impose limitations. Access can be selective based on aspects such as geographical regions (favouring users from European Member or Associated Countries), user group, thematic topic, or type of access (physical, virtual, remote). These limitations originate, e.g., from financial, political or organizational considerations.

In the past, users mostly relied on EU funding, for example via the INFRAIA TNA tool for financing their access to European atmospheric facilities. It is crucial that the science communities and RIs users, regardless of their origin, have clear and harmonised procedures and mechanisms for using and benefitting from the research facilities.

While most forms of access to facilities and digital services are in principle open to research communities from outside the European Member and Associated countries, atmospheric RIs are currently not organized with sustainable physical and remote access programs besides the specific case of EC funding in INFRAIA projects. Establishing long-term sustainable access will improve the position and scientific leadership of the European atmospheric RIs as a whole and support their strategic aim towards becoming truly Global Research Infrastructures.

This aim needs to be considered keeping in mind both EU-level and national strategies and targets, particularly in the current geopolitical era. In practice, liaising with RI-like organizations in other regions of the world, or directly with the agencies in specific countries, offers a potential to define conditions that would reinforce existing engagements to the benefit of European RIs. This kind of international collaboration will improve the global scientific capacity for providing tools to answer the UN SDGs (Societal Development Goals).

The aim of this deliverable is to summarize and analyze the challenges of international access provision based on the work done in the ATMO-ACCESS project and particularly based on a test

case from the Italian infrastructure project “ITINERIS” (Integrated Environmental Research Infrastructures System) [1]. A major part of the ITINERIS activities aim at promoting and supporting access to services provided by the Italian RIs to European Users and for Italian users to services provided by ACTRIS facilities. Based on the work done in ATMO-ACCESS and the test case, we provide recommendations to further develop the international access framework and modalities for atmospheric RIs.

2. Evaluation and analysis of challenges

The work in the ATMO-ACCESS project has identified and assessed a number of structural and emerging challenges that affect the feasibility and sustainability of international access to atmospheric research infrastructures (RIs). These challenges are rooted in funding mechanisms, legal and institutional frameworks, operational practices, and broader geopolitical considerations. This section summarizes key findings based on work carried out across multiple tasks and deliverables within ATMO-ACCESS.

2.1 Fragmented European funding landscape

A core issue is the reliance on project-based funding mechanisms, particularly the EC-supported INFRA-SERV TNA model. While highly successful in developing, harmonising and structuring, and facilitating access to RI services within Europe, this model is not financially viable in the long-term.

The analysis presented in Deliverable D3.1 [2] (Feedback document on access modalities from the perspective of the national stakeholders) and elaborated in D3.2 [3] (Report on modalities for co-funding physical and remote access with national stakeholders) summarizes the challenges in funding the access. TNA support through the European Commission is crucial, but access can be supported through national funding agencies, ministries and research councils with support from institutional budgets from the host organizations and in some cases co-funding from the users. In practice, the funding landscape of distributed RIs is fragmented and sustainable access shall be based on a synergy of diversified funding sources. Steps for putting it all together under one framework and pushing for joint access programmes, e.g., with EU and national funding agencies, are needed. The other key finding was the divergences in funding availability and mechanisms across countries and institutions.

In practice, outside the framework of Horizon Europe, sustainable and recurring funding for access remains limited.

2.2 Legal and administrative barriers

Legal and administrative heterogeneity across national systems presents a significant barrier to seamless international access to atmospheric research infrastructures. Each country, via its research performing organizations involved in operating research facilities, applies its own legal framework, administrative procedures, and institutional rules, which often do not align with one another. This fragmentation creates uncertainty for both users and access providers when planning and implementing international collaboration.

At a practical level, administrative burdens such as visa requirements, residency or work permits, and travel authorizations can significantly delay or even prevent researchers from outside the EU from accessing RI facilities in the EU. These issues are especially acute for researchers or users from countries with limited bilateral agreements in place. Furthermore, institutional approval processes for hosting foreign visitors or sharing resources vary widely between RPOs, institutions and countries, adding to the complexity and unpredictability of organizing coherent access.

Beyond these practical hurdles, there is a broader structural issue: the absence of harmonized access policies across the European RI landscape. Research infrastructures often operate under different access conditions, proposal evaluation criteria, and usage rights, making it difficult for users to understand the rules of engagement. This lack of consistency reduces transparency, limits comparability between facilities, and causes inefficient access management and inefficient use of available resources. For potential users from outside Europe, especially those unfamiliar with the EU's research ecosystem, this administrative opacity may be a major deterrent.

To facilitate more inclusive and equitable international access, it is essential to streamline administrative procedures and pursue greater alignment of access policies across RIs. Coordinated efforts to develop common frameworks, harmonised templates for agreements (e.g., financial support, access policies, Intellectual Property Rights connected to the outcomes of the access), and centralized access portals could help reduce friction and optimize the access management at the level of access-providing RPOs, as well as improve the user experience for global collaborators.

2.3 Limitations in institutional mandates and operational models

Many national atmospheric research facilities currently lack a formal mandate or strategic orientation to serve international users within the EU but also particularly those outside of EU-

funded frameworks. This is the case despite the fact that quite often there are national RI roadmaps in place. The primary mission of the national research facilities, as defined by national funding bodies or host institutions, is often focused on supporting domestic research priorities or fulfilling obligations within European-level projects such as those funded by Horizon Europe. As a result, international access—especially from non-EU countries—is typically not embedded in the core operational framework of these facilities.

This limitation became evident during the ATMO-ACCESS project, which observed that international access provision tends to be *ad hoc* or dependent on personal scientific networks rather than being part of a systematic or policy-driven approach. While European collaborations are relatively well-supported—especially when backed by EU funding instruments such as INFRA-SERV—access from outside this sphere is rarely addressed through structured programs or sustained by institutional mechanisms.

Furthermore, many facilities are not currently designed to support long-term, programmatic access for international users. Strategic planning documents often do not include internationalisation objectives, and there may be no dedicated resources or personnel assigned to manage international engagement. This absence of planning hampers the development of predictable, transparent, and inclusive access mechanisms.

In addition, while the pandemic accelerated the deployment of remote and virtual access tools, most facilities still lack the necessary infrastructure and organizational practices to scale these modes of access for sustained use, particularly for international users (for remote access). Services provided by virtual access are, by default, available to all users worldwide without geographical constraints. However, challenges regarding interoperability and Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-useable (FAIR) use in general are apparent as in many cases, digital tools remain fragmented, underutilized, or are only available through temporary project funding. Without investment in scalable remote access models and digital interoperability, European RIs and their international counterparts risk missing opportunities for broader global collaboration and knowledge exchange.

To move toward more inclusive and globally relevant research infrastructures, it is essential that national facilities incorporate international access into their long-term strategies. This includes establishing formal mandates, allocating resources for global engagement, and developing access modalities that extend beyond European RI consortia and EU funding programmes.

2.4 Geopolitical constraints

Scientific diplomacy, once largely insulated from political tensions, is now increasingly shaped by broader geopolitical considerations. Research infrastructures—particularly those with international reach—must operate within a rapidly evolving global context where science and technology are more frequently entangled with issues of national security, strategic autonomy, and economic competitiveness.

International cooperation in atmospheric research can be directly impacted by sanction regimes, shifting diplomatic alliances, and restrictions on dual-use technologies (i.e., technology that can be used for both civilian and military applications) or data sharing in general. These developments can influence institutional policies, limit researchers' mobility, or constrain access to certain resources, instruments, or collaborations. For example, political decisions at the national or EU level may prevent cooperation with specific countries or institutions, regardless of the scientific merit or shared environmental goals.

During ATMO-ACCESS, these realities were acknowledged as key external factors influencing the feasibility and sustainability of international access. We recognized that geopolitical uncertainties could disrupt existing partnerships or prevent the formation of new ones, particularly in regions where governance frameworks are fragile or politically sensitive.

In this context, European atmospheric RIs must adopt a resilient and adaptive approach to international engagement. This includes incorporating scenario-based planning into access strategies, where multiple geopolitical futures are considered, and contingency mechanisms are developed. The access policies should be considered as independently as possible from geopolitical context. It also means maintaining strategic flexibility—for example, by diversifying geographic partnerships, strengthening collaborations within stable multilateral frameworks (e.g., WMO-GAW, GEO), and ensuring that critical capabilities remain operable under changing political conditions.

Ultimately, the capacity of European RIs to act as trusted, neutral platforms for global science cooperation will depend on their ability to navigate these external pressures while upholding their scientific integrity and mission to serve global environmental goals.

2.5 Lack of Global Reciprocity and Balanced Partnerships

The RI landscape as it exists in Europe is unique and similar is missing on other continents. The access is commonly arranged on RPO or network level, and as there are no equivalent

counterparts to the EU RIs, the establishment and implementation of international frameworks for access is more complex.

European Research Infrastructures are generally open to international collaboration and have demonstrated strong scientific leadership through their participation in global initiatives and networks. However, despite this openness, reciprocal arrangements with non-EU partners remain the exception rather than the norm. While European facilities routinely host international users—often through EU-funded TNA schemes—there are few structured opportunities for European researchers to access equivalent facilities outside Europe under comparable conditions.

A key barrier to more balanced international collaboration is the absence of joint access schemes, in which access is co-designed and co-funded by EU and non-EU partners. Most of the existing access provisions are unilateral or based on project-specific agreements. Without long-term, formal mechanisms in place, it will remain difficult to ensure continuity, predictability, and fairness in how access is granted and supported across borders.

Similarly, cost-sharing agreements between European RIs and their international counterparts are scarce. The financial burden of hosting international users or participating in global campaigns often falls disproportionately on European facilities, particularly in the absence of contributions from non-European funders. This imbalance can disincentivize RIs from engaging in broader access provision and limits the potential for expanding collaborative research efforts on a global scale.

To overcome these limitations, there is a growing need to establish coordinated multilateral engagement frameworks from EU RIs with non-EU infrastructures. Although Memorandum of Understanding is typically bi-lateral, from one RI to another or between countries, there should be collaborative efforts e.g., in RIs and even between RIs to establish common templates and frameworks. Such frameworks should be underpinned by formalized and coordinated partnerships—including Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs), strategic cooperation agreements, or co-funded access programs—that explicitly define the terms of collaboration. These templates should address key aspects such as eligibility, access procedures, cost-sharing arrangements, intellectual property rights, and data governance.

Formal partnerships not only help to ensure mutual benefits and access symmetry, but also contribute to trust-building, alignment of strategic objectives, long-term sustainability of international collaboration as well as visibility of the facilities. By moving beyond informal or ad hoc relationships, European RIs can position themselves as core actors within a truly global

research infrastructure ecosystem—one that is equipped to address shared environmental challenges and contribute meaningfully to international scientific and policy agendas.

3. Recommendations for International Access Modalities

Based on the analysis of challenges in international access provision presented in Section 2 and drawing from the collective experience of the ATMO-ACCESS project, this section outlines key recommendations to enhance the sustainability, inclusiveness, and strategic alignment of access modalities to European atmospheric research infrastructures. The recommendations are structured thematically to address funding, legal and policy frameworks, operational coherence, digital tools, and partnership models.

3.1 Towards Sustainable and Inclusive Funding Mechanisms

To ensure the long-term viability of access, including from international users, it is essential to move beyond reliance on temporary project-based instruments such as INFRA-SERV and to develop sustainable co-funding models that integrate national, regional, and European funding sources. This includes:

- Engaging national funding agencies to co-finance access for both domestic and European / international users, particularly for physical and remote access.
- Linking TNA funding with national strategic priorities, such as national Green Deal implementations or cohesion policy funds (e.g., European Regional Development Fund), to secure long-term investment in access provision.
- Promoting innovative and integrating co-funding practices, such as the best test case “ITINERIS” in Italy serving as a promising model. ITINERIS [3] gathers several national RIs from different research fields connecting and harmonizing their activities and access provision. The project funds access for Italian users to EU facilities, and inversely provides funding for EU and international users to access Italian facilities. The initiative demonstrates how national funds can be used to support access to RI services, aligning with European priorities while fostering domestic scientific capacity.
- Ensuring science funding frameworks to include Physical Access (PA) to the comprehensive observational facilities to facilitate advancement of science.

- Extending funding frameworks to cover Virtual Access (VA) recognizing the growing importance of digital services in research workflows, particularly access to added value services, which require funding for development and maintenance.
- Encouraging participation from international stakeholders and third countries in joint funding schemes in connection with national and European research grants to enhance reciprocity and diversify the user base.
- Encouraging national RI funding to acknowledge added value to support international access to the research facilities.
- Improving efficient use of national and European level grants for supporting international access provision improving the use of the RI services and potentially providing additional support through user fees.

3.2 Harmonizing Access Policies and Procedures

To overcome administrative fragmentation and support a smoother user experience, there is a need to develop common or interoperable access frameworks across European RIs and globally. While full harmonization may be challenging, the following steps are recommended:

- Consider development of a common access portal or interoperable access management systems that allow users to identify and apply for access across multiple RIs through a single interface or coordinated system.
- Ensure that access procedures are transparent, multilingual, and easy to navigate, particularly for international users unfamiliar with European research ecosystems.
- Promote alignment of access eligibility criteria, review processes, and reporting standards to reduce administrative burden and foster comparability across facilities.

3.3 Enhancing Monitoring and Impact Assessment

As access to RIs becomes more complex and diversified, robust monitoring and reporting tools are essential to ensure accountability, demonstrate impact, and support strategic planning. Impact assessment greatly relies on the actual outcome of access, such as data and high-impact publications. The tracking of the outcomes needs to be improved. We recommend:

- Developing automated reporting functionalities within the access portal to capture data across the full lifecycle of access (e.g., application, selection, implementation, and outcome).
- Generating summary dashboards or data visualizations of access flows and statistics of relevant criteria (e.g., user group, country, thematic area, and access type).
- Using this data to perform periodic reviews, policy dialogue with funders, and external communication on the societal and scientific value of RI access.
- Acknowledging the challenges in timelines: the time from the access to scientific outcomes and impacts can span years or even decades. Continuous monitoring and periodic re-assessments are recommended.

3.4 Strengthening Global Collaboration and Reciprocity

There is a clear need to formalize global collaborations in terms of RI access. The suite of TNA projects in the atmospheric science field (ACTRIS, ACTRIS-2, ATMO-ACCESS, EUROCHAMP-1, EUROCHAMP-2, EUROCHAMP-2020) shows that more than 10% of access has been provided to international users.

To establish Europe's RIs as global players, access strategies must embrace reciprocity and equitable partnerships. This requires:

- Formalizing bilateral or multilateral agreements with non-European RIs that include provisions for mutual access, joint calls, and shared infrastructure use. Leverage can be taken on the on-going EU-project CARGO-ACT [4] in terms of EU-US collaboration and connect to access initiatives between EU and China described in ATMO-ACCESS Deliverable 3.3.
- Encouraging reciprocal access opportunities for European researchers to use non-European facilities under similar conditions, supported by aligned funding mechanisms.
- Supporting the co-development of global and regional services with international partners, ensuring knowledge exchange and capacity building.

3.5 Clarifying the Relationship Between Access and Open Data

While the principle of open data is widely endorsed, the relationship between access to physical infrastructures and access to the data they produce requires clarification. The current limiting

factor to that is the RI capability and capacity to systematically archive data resulting from access. We recommend:

- Distinguishing between access to facilities (e.g., instruments, labs, platforms) and access to the resulting data, especially when access is granted through public funding mechanisms.
- Developing policies that clearly define rights and obligations for data use, co-authorship, and attribution when data is generated through transnational or international access.
- Ensuring that access to open data remains unrestricted, while still recognizing and crediting the infrastructure and users involved in its generation.

3.6 Strategic Planning and Stakeholder Engagement

Ultimately, achieving sustainable and inclusive access modalities requires the engagement of both national and international stakeholders, including policymakers, funding agencies, and research-performing organizations. Key actions include:

- Embedding international access within the long-term strategic plans of RIs and national roadmaps. This requires continuous interaction between the national consortia and the RIs as well as commitment of the national stakeholders and funders.
- Involving external stakeholders in co-designing access frameworks to ensure relevance, feasibility, and political support.
- Establishing or strengthening coordination mechanisms at the EU level (e.g., through ESFRI, the European Open Science Cloud, or the RI Monitoring and Evaluation System) to align efforts and monitor progress.

4. Conclusions and Outlook

The ATMO-ACCESS project has demonstrated that while European atmospheric Research Infrastructures are inherently international in their scope and scientific relevance, the practical implementation of international access remains constrained by a range of structural, administrative, financial, and strategic challenges. Section 2 of this deliverable identified key barriers to global access provision, including fragmented funding models, legal and institutional heterogeneity, limited reciprocity, and operational mismatches across RIs. These issues are compounded by evolving geopolitical realities and the need for greater digital interoperability.

In response, the recommendations outlined in Section 3 provide a thematic roadmap for advancing international access modalities. Key priorities include developing co-funding mechanisms at both EU and national levels, improving procedural harmonization through interoperable access systems, fostering reciprocal partnerships beyond Europe, and enhancing monitoring and reporting of access activities. The growing role of virtual access and the need to clearly separate infrastructure access from open data provision were also highlighted as areas requiring further attention.

Looking ahead, a transition towards sustainable, inclusive, and globally connected access frameworks is essential to reinforce the scientific leadership of European atmospheric RIs and support their evolution into truly Global Research Infrastructures. This transformation will require coordinated action among national governments, funding agencies, RI operators, and international partners.

To sustain the momentum established during ATMO-ACCESS, we recommend the following next steps:

- Institutionalize the recommendations through national RI roadmaps and strategic planning documents.
- Leverage good practices identified in the project, such as the ITINERIS model in Italy, as inspiration for national co-funding approaches.
- Engage with global scientific and policy platforms to position European RIs as key contributors to address shared environmental challenges, including the UN Sustainable Development Goals.
- Ensure continuity beyond the ATMO-ACCESS project by integrating these recommendations into ongoing RI development efforts (e.g., within ESFRI, EOSC, or the European RI Monitoring Framework).

By taking these steps, European atmospheric research infrastructures can move decisively towards more equitable, transparent, and long-term international access models—models that not only serve the scientific community but also support global environmental policy and capacity building.

5. References

[1] The ITINERIS project: <https://itineris.cnr.it/>

ATMO ACCESS
Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

[2] ATMO-ACCESS Deliverable 3.1: [Feedback document on access modalities from the perspective of the national stakeholders](#)

[3] ATMO-ACCESS Deliverable 3.2: [Report on modalities for co-funding physical and remote access with national stakeholders](#)

[4] The CARGO-ACT project: <https://www.cargo-act.eu/>

This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme through the ATMO-ACCESS Integrating Activity under grant agreement No 101008004

atmo-access.eu